

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SCULPTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
MODERN FINE ART OF UZBEKISTAN****Rakhimov Khasanboy Umarjon ugli**

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Annotation: This article provides information about reforms in the field of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the role of sculpture in the development of fine arts.

Key words: sculptor, sculpture, art, culture, reform, academy, visual arts, period.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi madaniyat, san'at sohasidagi islohotlar, haykaltaroshlik san'ati, haykaltaroshlik sohasining tasviriy san'at sohasining rivojlanishdagi o'rni haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: haykaltarosh, haykaltaroshlik, san'at, madaniyat, islohot, akademiya, tasviriy san'at, davr.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о реформах в области культуры и искусства в Республике Узбекистан, роли скульптуры в развитии изобразительного искусства.

Ключевые слова: скульптор, скульптура, искусство, культура, реформа, академия, изобразительное искусство, период.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

In Uzbekistan, in the new historical period that began in the 1990s, sculpture, along with other forms of art, underwent remarkable creative changes. In addition to the new cultural policy, the creation of a healthy spiritual environment in the country, the restoration of national traditions, and the realization of our historical identity became a priority, and as a result, a process of creative renewal was created on this front. The way to a new qualitative stage, different from the previous methodological approaches, has been opened. Such changes in artistic life created the necessary creative environment for the development of Uzbek fine art, including sculpture. Exciting feelings such as being inspired by independence, honoring national values, and being proud of the rich cultural heritage of the past made a new creative turn. First, the issue of national interpretation, which has not gained a serious level until now, has risen to the leading position. One of the most important approaches was to enrich the shaped buildings with national details and to ensure the proportionality of the composite structure to the modern space. "It should be said that during the former Soviet regime, this field became the most ideological type of art." [4]

After the establishment of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan in 1997, the process of development in sculpture in harmony with the active directions of world art accelerated. Among the sculptors, it began to be seen that they are trying to open the world of images with the help of new plastic forms and materials. They are rushing to create works that are completely free from traditional sculptural features - prone to modern environment, new technical development and changes in people's thinking. On the one hand, this situation affects the narrowing of the scope of the realistic direction, but on the other hand, it is in line with modern development. It can be understood from the above that the current period of creative renewal has created a tendency to develop a national trend in monumental sculpture, and to assimilate the experiences of the global artistic process in the local section in the field of easels, and created the necessary opportunity for the future development of both types. The composition can be found in music, theatre, photography, literature, and all kinds of fine arts. [5]

It is known from the world sculptural experience that plastic monuments serve to express the great figures of the nation, the vision of the events corresponding to a certain historical period, and the advanced ideological propaganda of the society. The majestic sculptures of the 1990s are based on this goal and express the ideological concepts of the new cultural life. The sculptors' serious awareness of new requirements, methodological approaches, and especially

working in accordance with modern standards brought new talents to the surface.

In particular, Ilhom Jabbarov, Kamal Jabbarov, Jaloliddin Mirtojiev, Anvar Rakhmatullaev stand out among them. In this regard, it is worth noting that the work of Ilhom Jabbarov and Jaloliddin Mirtojiev is more characteristic of the work of professional skill. Based on a new creative opportunity, they embodied the image of Amir Temur, which has been a problem for many years, as well as objectively interpreted the statue of thinkers such as Alisher Navoi, Shah Mashrab, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Mirzo Babur, and the spirit of the local school was revived. The main criteria for development are the figurines of the second type of local sculptors, decorative ornaments and garden sculptures [6].

Jaloliddin Mirtojiev, who became known in the 1990s for his monumental sculpture, achieved good results in a short period of time. During his career, he formed creative qualities such as the balance of form and idea, the fluency of artistic expression. In the work of Jaloliddin Mirtojiev, the forms are somewhat free, rich in plastic movement, and the compositional solution of the overall image is worthy of attention, while the images are directly related to important scenes from the past life. In the 1980s, under the guidance of the experienced sculptor F. Grishenko, he fully mastered artistic education, which became fully visible in his works. Although it entered the field of creativity in the 80s, the period of its main maturity corresponds to the 1990s. He worked effectively in both spheres of sculpture - majestic and easel type, and showed expressiveness typical of poetry in his works. Recently, he fulfilled orders for Russia ("Hazrat Navoi" 2002, "Mirzo Ulugbek" 2002), Japan ("Alisher Navoi", 2003), China ("Kamoliddin Behzod", 2003). In the new historical period, "Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur" (Andijan, 1993), "Abdulla Qadiri" (Tashkent, 1994), "Cholpon" (Andijan, 1997), "Abdurauf Fitrat" (Bukhara, 1997), "Elbek" (Tashkent) , 1998), executed large sculptures worthy of attention, such as "Mourning Mother" (Jizzakh 1999, Andijon 2001, Fergana 2002). Alakhusus, during the authoritarian system, the monuments dedicated to the victims of repression, such as Abdulla Qadiri, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Elbek, Abdurauf Fitrat, who were concerned about the country's prospects and national culture, and were martyred on this path, are clearly distinguished by their inner feelings stands. This is achieved through the mental and spiritual development of the students.[7]

It would not be wrong to say that the monument to Amir Temur, erected in Tashkent in 1993, and in Samarkand and Shakhrizabz in 1996, is a vivid example

of the change that occurred in the new historical and ideological life. Among them, the statue in our capital stands out with its magnificent image. Based on the requirements of majestic art, this monument was created to make it easy to fully perceive the image of the Master from a distance and near. In his creative approach, the public gaze of the new era, festive atmosphere was taken into account and the spirit of independence was deeply expressed.[8]

The compositional interpretation of the statue, carried out in accordance with the ideological solution, represents the idea of victory in its general structure. The right side of the statue (from the front view) can be called the characteristic center of the proportions of the plastic form. Also, a remarkable artistic solution can be observed in the half view from the front and left side. The majestic and dignified appearance of the monument is clearly visible from the right angle. The image of a patriot and just ruler is revealed in the noble appearance of the great person.

The statue of Amir Temur installed in Samarkand was made on the basis of the work of the well-known artist Malik Nabiev, which was accepted as a standard (confirmed to be close to the original), and several deep meanings were embodied in the structure of the artistic composition. Also, the statue of Amir Temur in Oksaroy deserves attention. [9] He is also depicted in a majestic appearance, like the statue in Tashkent. Amir Temur's three large statues in Tashkent, Samarkand and Shakhrisabz have different views and ideas, and the artistic repetitive aspects of the monuments can be felt in their portraits.

In short, the ideological conditions of the 1990s created a new stage in the development of sculpture. Now, unlike the previous creative traditions, this field has begun to develop only on a local basis. As we have witnessed, the expansion of the range of national themes in majestic sculpture eventually led to the formation of new creative principles and methodological approaches that were not observed in the previous period, which in turn indicates that the sculpture of Uzbekistan in the 1990s was rising in national status.

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9. Created in 1996 by sculptors I. Jabborov, K. Jabborov, architect. B. Usmonov, M. Mustafoevlar, the size of the statue is 9 meters, the base is 7 meters, it is made of bronze.